

The Effect of the Traffic Light Labeling System upon Students' Food Choices in a University Dining Center

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine if implementing a traffic light labeling system would affect students' food choices in a university dining center. Data collection occurred on two separate days, four weeks apart. Survey questionnaires were distributed to 165 participants and 181 participants in the pre- and post-implementation phases of the study, respectively. When controlling for usual diet healthiness, a greater percentage of participants selected healthier food choices following the implementation of the traffic light labeling system. The results from this study reflected those from prior research, which found the traffic light labeling system affected participants' food choices.

Keywords: food choices, traffic light labeling, students

Background Information

Nutrition labeling systems are used in various foodservice operations to help consumers make informed food choices. There are many types of nutrition labeling systems currently in use today. Some examples include: the traffic light labeling system, "Smart Choice" labels, front-of-package labels, and physical activity equivalent nutrition labels. Previous studies have shown that of the many nutritional labeling systems available, the traffic light labeling system is potentially the most effective in providing information to consumers trying to make healthy food choices (Borgmeier & Westenhoefer, 2009).

The traffic light labeling system is the process of applying a green, yellow, or red-colored label to foods, indicating the healthiness of that food (Faculty of Public Health, 2008). Foods with a green-colored label (recommended to consume often) are determined to be healthier than foods with a yellow-colored label (recommended to consume in moderation) or foods with a red-colored label (considered the least healthy). Foods with red-colored labels do not need to be completely eliminated from one's diet; instead, they should be considered as a treat and consumed only occasionally. The traffic light labeling system can aid individuals in quickly making more informed and healthier food choices (Babio et al., 2013).

Consumers may have a better perception of the healthiness of foods when, for example, comparing a red label to a yellow label, or a yellow label to a green label (Hieke & Wilczynski, 2012). Because the traffic

light labeling system can be utilized in real life buying situations, it is important to understand how this system could help increase the knowledge and general awareness of consumers while making food choices.

A study by Borgmeier and Westenhoefer (2009) examined four different nutritional labeling formats to see which one best helped retail customers differentiate healthier food products from less healthy ones. Of the four formats, the traffic light labeling system was found to have the greatest effect upon participants' food choices. This study also found that the absence of a nutrition label resulted in a lower percentage of participants selecting healthy foods. Studies have shown that there is a need for a nutrition labeling system that can be clearly understood by the average consumer to help them to make healthy food choices (McCann et al., 2013). For example, a study by Snelling and Kennard (2009) found that there was a decrease in the sale of red-labeled food items after implementing a traffic light labeling system.

Traffic light labeling systems have aided consumers' food choices not only in commercial establishments but also in onsite foodservice operations. A study conducted by Thorndike, Riis, Sonnenberg, and Levy (2014) in a large hospital cafeteria found that the traffic light labeling system had a sustained improvement upon healthy versus unhealthy food and beverage purchases of a diverse population. The biggest change occurred with beverage choices, with a 39% decrease in unhealthy beverage purchases during the span of the study (Thorndike et al., 2014).

Research of university students' perceptions of food and healthiness showed that university students had well-developed ideas of the healthiness of food that extended beyond simple calorie-counting, suggesting that additional labeling information is useful to help guide students' food choices (Fernandes, de Oliveira, Rodrigues, Fiates, & da Costa Proença, 2015). Peterson, Duncan, Null, Roth, and Gill (2010) conducted an intervention using healthy choice indicators and signs in a university dining center. The researchers found that their intervention helped increase the healthy choices of the university students, as evidenced by a self-reported increase in awareness and a significant increase in the consumption of healthful foods (Peterson et al., 2010). During a pilot implementation of a traffic light labeling system in a university cafeteria, food items students considered healthy actually turned out to be some of the unhealthiest items in the cafeteria (Davis & Prakash, 2013).

The purpose of this study was to determine if implementing a traffic light labeling system would affect college students' food choices in a university dining center. To the best of the authors' knowledge, no prior studies conducted in university dining centers had utilized a cycle menu during a one-meal implementation of a traffic light labeling system. Thus, this served as the framework for the study.

Methodology

Study Design

This research study was conducted in a mid-sized private university located in the Midwestern region of the United States (U.S.). The study was approved by the university's institutional research board and data collection was performed in one of the university's two dining centers. A mean population of

approximately 500 students typically visited this dining center for dinner from 5:00 p.m. – 7:30 p.m. each evening, seven days per week, during the regular academic school year (August – May).

During dinner at the dining center, potential participants were offered the opportunity to complete paper and pencil surveys that contained a series of open-ended and multiple-choice questions. Individuals who agreed to participate in the research study completed their surveys during dinner, after they had gone through the cafeteria line and had made their food choices for the evening. The surveys included questions about participants' food and beverage choices and the factors that may have influenced their choices. Participants also responded to questions relating to gender, their weekly stress level, and how healthy they normally ate.

Survey data were collected in the dining center in two phases: before implementing a traffic light labeling system (pre-implementation phase), and four weeks later, after implementing a traffic light labeling system (post-implementation phase). The dining center used a cycle menu, which repeated after four weeks. The two phases of survey data collection were conducted four weeks apart, on the same day of the week (Wednesday), in the same dining center, using the same dinner menu. This helped to ensure that data from both phases were sufficiently comparable.

During the pre-implementation phase, the dining center used nutritional food identifier cards during meal service. These were laminated 3" x 5" index cards containing nutrition information, which were placed next to the respective food items offered during each dinner meal. This was a normal, standard operating procedure and the food identifier cards were regularly used during dinner throughout the school year for all main food items. A pre-implementation survey was used to determine if participants noticed the food identifier cards and if the cards had an effect upon their food choices.

During the post-implementation phase (four weeks later), a traffic light labeling system was implemented by simply affixing a 3/4-inch circular green, yellow, or red-colored sticker to the regularly-used nutritional food identifier cards (see Figure 1). In addition, a 2' x 3' informational poster describing the traffic light labeling system was prominently displayed at the entrance to the dining center (see Figure 2). All participants in this study had to walk past the informational poster prior to going through the cafeteria line to make their food choices.

The post-implementation survey was used to determine if participants noticed the newly-implemented traffic light labeling system and/or informational poster and if those items had an effect upon their food choices. It was postulated that the traffic light labeling system implemented on the food identifier cards along with the prominently displayed 2' x 3' informational poster would influence participants' food choices.

Participants and Procedures

Potential participants included university students who ate in the dining center during dinner meal service. Individuals who were not students and individuals under 18 years of age were excluded from data collection. Potential participants were asked if they would be interested in completing a paper and pencil survey, and were also informed of the option to participate in a drawing for three gift cards as an incentive for completing the survey. Individuals who agreed to participate in the study were instructed to

complete the surveys in the dining room and return them directly to the researchers. Surveys were pilot tested in the dining center a week prior to each phase of formal data collection. Two rounds of formal data collection were conducted in the dining center, four weeks apart. For all phases of data collection activity, including pilot testing, participants were not individually identifiable and their survey responses were kept confidential.

Data Analysis

Survey data were entered into SPSS (IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 23.0. Armonk, NY: IBM Corporation) and verified for accuracy. Descriptive statistics, correlations, frequencies, independent samples t-tests, and ANCOVAs were utilized during the data analysis. Statistical significance was measured at the $p \leq .05$ level.

Results

Demographics

A total of 165 participants completed the pre-implementation survey and 181 participants completed the post-implementation survey. Overall, 180 participants were male (52.0%) and 165 were female (47.7%), with one person not indicating their sex.

Survey Responses

Participants' selected responses for the pre-implementation and post-implementation phases of the study are shown below. Comparisons of responses between the pre-implementation and post-implementation surveys are given, along with responses germane to each survey.

How many times a week do you eat dinner at the dining center? From the pre-implementation survey, participants reported eating at the dining center an average of 4.92 times per week. From the post-implementation survey, participants reported eating at the dining center an average of 4.95 times per week.

Do you think there is a variety of healthy choices for dinner in the dining center? From the pre-implementation survey, 79.4% of the participants said that there were a variety of healthy choices and 20.6% said that there were not. From the post-implementation survey, 75.1% of the participants said that there were a variety of healthy choices, 23.2% said that there were not a variety of healthy food choices, and three participants did not answer this question.

What were your food choices today? Twenty of the main food items from the cafeteria were listed on the surveys. Following data collection, participants' responses were categorized based upon nutritional information and assigned classifications of "all green", "mostly green", "mostly yellow", "all yellow", "mostly red", or "all red" (see Table 1).

What affected your food choices today? Factors affecting students' food choices are shown in Table 2. From the pre-implementation survey, participants' other factors included being on a soft foods diet, allergies, and that food choices were better than the other dining center on campus. From the post-implementation survey, participants' other factors included food allergies, diet changes due to surgery, and vegetarian items.

Do you notice the food identifier cards? From the pre-implementation survey, 81.8% of participants reported that they noticed the existing food identifier cards.

Did you read and understand the nutritional information provided on the food identifier cards? From the pre-implementation survey, 52.1% of the participants of the pre-implementation phase said they understood the information on the food identifier cards and 30.9% said they did not.

Did you notice the traffic light labeling system? From the post-implementation survey, 60.8% of the participants reported that they noticed the implemented traffic light labeling system.

Do you know what the different colors in the traffic light system represent? From the post-implementation survey, 52% of the post-implementation participants said that they did know what the different colors in the implemented traffic light system represented and 48% of the participants said that they did not.

How healthy would you consider your regular diet to be? From the pre-implementation survey, 20.0% reported their regular diet as healthy, 60.0% reported somewhat healthy, 17.0% reported somewhat unhealthy, and 3.0% reported unhealthy. From the post-implementation survey, 17.2% reported their regular diet as healthy, 62.2% reported somewhat healthy, 17.8% reported somewhat unhealthy, and 2.8% reported unhealthy.

Do you classify foods as “good” or “bad”? From the pre-implementation survey, 86.1% of participants reported that they did classify foods as “good” or “bad” and 13.9% reported that they did not. From the post-implementation survey, 85.0% of participants reported that they did classify foods as “good” or “bad” and 15.0% reported that they did not.

What would you say your weekly stress levels are? Participants were asked about their weekly stress levels. Results for the pre- and post-implementation surveys are shown in Table 3.

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA)

A one-way ANCOVA testing food choices between the pre-implementation and the post implementation groups controlling for reported stress levels and usual healthiness of diet was conducted using SPSS (IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 23.0. Armonk, NY: IBM Corporation). Usual healthiness of diet was found to be a statistically significant covariate, $F(1, 338) = 41.33, p < .001$ (see Table 4). When controlling for usual healthiness of diet, there was a statistically significant difference between the pre-implementation and post-implementation group on participants' food choices $F(1, 338) = 20.61, p < .001$ (see Table 4). On a six-point Likert scale, with “1” being “all green” items and “6” being “all red” items, the traffic light labeling post-implementation group ($M = 3.05, SD = 1.29$) chose healthier foods than the pre-implementation group ($M = 3.64, SD = 1.28$), when controlling for usual healthiness of diet.

Discussion and Conclusions

The purpose of this study was to determine if implementing a traffic light labeling system would affect students' food choices in a university dining center. The food identifier card group selected more "red" or "mostly red" food choices (and fewer "green" or "mostly green" food choices) during the pre-implementation phase. Conversely, the traffic light labeling group selected fewer "red" or "mostly red" food choices (and more "green" or "mostly green" food choices) during the post-implementation phase. When controlling for usual diet healthiness, the traffic light labeling group (post-implementation) chose healthier foods than did the food identifier card group (pre-implementation). The results from this study reflected those from a prior study by Thorndike et al. (2014), which found that the traffic light labeling system had an effect upon participants' food choices.

Previous studies have noted that a lack of knowledge is a factor that contributes to unhealthy eating patterns (Elbel, 2011; Krukowski, Harvey-Berino, Kolodinsky, Narsana, & DeSisto, 2006). Furthermore, food labeling interventions can take an extended period of time to change individuals' food choice behaviors (Thorndike et al., 2014). However, this study demonstrated an effect upon students' food choices following implementation of a traffic light labeling system in just in one meal.

Limitations and Implications for Future Research

The short implementation length of the traffic light labeling system was a limiting factor in this research study. The traffic light labeling system was only implemented in the university dining center for one dinner meal. Future studies could explore whether there would be a lasting effect upon students' food choices if the traffic light labeling system was implemented for a greater length of time.

The traffic light labeling system was based only on total calories, total fat, and saturated fat for food items. In addition, the traffic light labeling system only described the total calories and sugar content for beverages. Future studies might explore augmenting the traffic light labeling system with information about vitamin and mineral content. The addition of these criteria could potentially have a further effect upon participants' food choices. Future studies could also explore if the traffic light labeling system would affect customers' food choices in various types of commercial foodservice operations.

References

- Babio, N., Vicent, P., López, L., Benito, A., Basulto, J., & Salas-Salvadó, J. (2014). Adolescents' ability to select healthy food using two different front-of-pack food labels: a cross-over study. *Public Health Nutrition*, *17*(6), 1403-1409. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1368980013001274>
- Borgmeier, I., & Westenhoefer, J. (2009). Impact of different food label formats on healthiness evaluation and food choice of consumers: a randomized-controlled study. *BMC Public Health*, *9*, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-9-184>
- Davis, S., & Prakash, A. (2013). A pilot study to develop nutritional guidance signage for a university cafeteria based on a traffic light design. *Journal of Foodservice Management and Education*, *7*(1), 33-38. Retrieved from <http://fsmec.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/05/7-1-Davis.pdf>
- Elbel, B. (2011). Consumer estimation of recommended and actual calories at fast food restaurants. *Obesity*, *19*(10), 1971-1978. <https://doi.org/10.1038/oby.2011.214>
- Faculty of Public Health. (2008). Traffic-light food labelling. Retrieved from http://www.fph.org.uk/uploads/ps_food_labelling.pdf

- Fernandes, A. C., de Oliveira, R. C., Rodrigues, V. M., Fiates, G. R., & da Costa Proença, R. P. (2015). Perceptions of university students regarding calories, food healthiness, and the importance of calorie information in menu labelling. *Appetite*, *91*, 173-178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2015.04.042>
- Hieke, S., & Wilczynski, P. (2012). Colour me in – an empirical study on consumer responses to the traffic light signposting system in nutrition labelling. *Public Health Nutrition*, *15*(5), 773-782. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1368980011002874>
- Krukowski, R. A., Harvey-Berino, J., Kolodinsky, J., Narsana, R. T., & DeSisto, T. P. (2006). Consumers may not use or understand calorie labeling in restaurants. *Journal of the American Dietetic Association*, *106*(6), 917-920. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jada.2006.03.005>
- McCann, M. T., Wallace, J. M., Robson, P. J., Rennie, K. L., McCaffrey, T. A., Welch, R. W., & Livingstone, M. E. (2013). Influence of nutrition labelling on food portion size consumption. *Appetite*, *65*, 153-158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2013.02.013>
- Peterson, S., Duncan, D. P., Null, D. B., Roth, S. L., & Gill, L. (2010). Positive changes in perceptions and selections of healthful foods by college students after a short-term point-of-selection intervention at a dining hall. *Journal of American College Health*, *58*(5), 425-431. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07448480903540457>
- Snelling, A. M., & Kennard, T. (2009). The impact of nutrition standards on competitive food offerings and purchasing behaviors of high school students. *Journal of School Health*, *79*(11), 541-546. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1746-1561.2009.00446.x>
- Thorndike, A. N., Riis, J., Sonnenberg, L. M., & Levy, D. E. (2014). Traffic-light labels and choice architecture promoting healthy food choices. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, *46*(2), 143-149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2013.10.002>

Table 1: Participants' food choices (n=342)

	All green	Mostly green	Mostly yellow	All yellow	Mostly red	All red	Total
Pre	3.6%	14.5%	40.0%	0%	40.0%	1.8%	100%
Post	8.3%	27.2%	40.0%	1.1%	22.2%	1.1%	100%

Note: Participants were asked the following question: “What were your food choices today?” Following data collection, participants’ responses were categorized based upon nutritional information and assigned classifications of “all green”, “mostly green”, “mostly yellow”, “all yellow”, “mostly red”, or “all red”.

Table 2: Factors affecting participants' food choices (n=342)

	Stress	Food cravings	Convenience	Appearance of Food	Other Factors
Pre	9.1%	30.9%	18.2%	34.5%	7.3%
Post	5.0%	28.7%	23.8%	39.2%	3.3%

Note: Participants were asked the following question: “What affected your food choices today?” Participants were given the options of “stress”, “food cravings”, “convenience”, “appearance of food”, and “other factors” to choose from.

Table 3: Participants' stress levels (n=342)

	No Stress	Moderate Stress	Very Stressed	Overly Stressed	No response
Pre	5.5%	59.4%	27.3%	7.9%	0.0%
Post	7.2%	55.8%	26.5%	9.4%	1.1%

Note: Participants were asked the following question: "What is your weekly stress level?" Participants were given the options of "no stress", "moderate stress", "very stressed", and "overly stressed" to choose from.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of food choices between the pre-implementation and the post implementation groups, controlling for reported stress levels and usual healthiness of diet (n=342)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	Observed Power
Corrected Model	90.903	3	20.659	.000	.155	1.000
Intercept	102.239	1	69.706	.000	.171	1.000
Stress Level	3.387	1	2.309	.130	.007	.329
Usual Diet Healthiness	60.614	1	41.326	.000	.109	1.000
Pre- and Post-Implementation	30.234	1	20.613	.000	.057	.995
Error	495.752	338				
Total	4400.000	342				
Corrected Total	586.655	341				

Note: Participants were asked the following questions: "What were your food choices today?" "What are your weekly stress levels: (a) no stress; (b) moderately stressed; (c) very stressed; and (d) overly stressed"; and "How healthy would you consider your regular diet to be: (a) healthy; (b) somewhat healthy; (c) somewhat unhealthy; (d) unhealthy." An ANCOVA was used to determine the relationship between food choices of the pre-implementation and post-implementation phase controlling for weekly stress levels and usual diet healthiness. Statistical significance was measured at the $p \leq .05$ level.

Figure 1: Nutritional food identifier card with an affixed green-colored traffic light label

Figure 2: Traffic light labeling informational poster, displayed at the dining center entrance

 = Choose Occasionally

Food Entree

Substance	Green	Yellow	Red
Calories	Less than 200 kcal	Between 200 and 350 kcal	More than 350 kcal
Total Fat	Less than 3g	Between 3 and 17.5g	More than 17.5g
Saturated Fat	Less than 2g	Between 2g and 5g	More than 5g

Side Dish and Dessert

Substance	Green	Yellow	Red
Calories	Less than 100 kcal	Between 100 and 200 kcal	More than 200 kcal
Total Fat	Less than 2g	Between 3g and 10g	More than 10g
Saturated Fat	Less than 1g	Between 2g and 4g	More than 4g

Drinks and Condiments

Substance	Green	Yellow	Red
Calories	Less than 50 kcal	Between 50 and 100 kcal	More than 100 kcal
	Less than 2.5g	Between 2.5g and 11g	More than 11g